

Supporting Information

to

pH sensing and imaging in living cells based on fluorescence lifetime of carbon dot nanosensors

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Reagents and materials

RhB (TCI Chemicals, $\geq 95\%$), NaOH (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 98\%$), and HCl (Lach-Ner, 35%) were used as received. All aqueous solutions were prepared using Milli-Q water (Millipore, USA). Dialysis tubing (0.1–0.5 kDa molecular weight cut-off) was purchased from Spectrum Chemical.

Characterization methods

TEM images were acquired on a JEOL 2010 transmission electron microscope operating at 160 kV. AFM images were acquired using an NTegra Spectra microscope (NT-MDT) with a NSG30 SS/10 probe. Topography scans were performed at a frequency of 0.3 Hz under ambient condition. Prior to measurement, the sample was diluted, drop-cast onto freshly cleaved muscovite mica, and allowed to dry. Cleanliness of the mica substrate was verified beforehand through supplementary AFM scans. XPS analysis was performed on a PHI VersaProbe II (Physical Electronics, USA) spectrometer with an Al K α source (15 kV, 50 W). FTIR spectra were collected on a Nicolet iS5 FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA) with the Smart Orbit ZnSe ATR technique.

Spectroscopy measurements

UV–vis absorption spectra were recorded using a Specord S600 spectrometer (Analytik Jena, Germany). Steady-state and transient fluorescence measurements were performed on an FLS980 fluorescence spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments, UK) equipped with a 450 W xenon arc lamp and EPL-375 ps pulsed diode laser ($\lambda_{em} = 372$ nm, pulse width: 66.5 ps, repetition rate: 10 MHz, average power: 75 μ W; Edinburgh Instruments, UK) as excitation sources. The instrument response function (IRF) was obtained using a dilute LUDOX scattering solution. Fluorescence decay curves were fitted using a stretched exponential function ($I(t) = I_0 e^{-(t/\tau)^\beta}$, where τ is the fluorescence decay time and β is the stretch parameter) or biexponential function ($I(t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 B_i \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right)$, $\sum_{i=1}^n B_i = 1$, where τ_i is the decay time constants and B_i are the normalized amplitudes of the each components; the amplitude weighted average decay lifetime τ_{avg} of the entire PL decay process was calculated with the form: $\tau_{avg} = \sum B_i \tau_i^2 / \sum B_i \tau_i$). Temperature-dependent fluorescence measurements were conducted using a variable-temperature liquid nitrogen optical cryostat OptistatDN2 controlled by a cryogenic programmable temperature controller MercuryITC (Oxford Instruments, UK) with a temperature stability of ± 0.1 K (measured over 10 min). Time-resolved fluorescence spectra at different temperatures (0–42 $^\circ$ C) were recorded under identical instrument settings.

Each solution with specified pH values (1.0–13.0) was adjusted to the appropriate final pH 1 M HCl or 1 M NaOH, and pH values were measured using a calibrated pH meter. Solutions with specified ionic strengths (0–4.6 M) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of KCl.

Fluorescence quantum yield measurements

Fluorescence QY was determined using an absolute method on the same fluorescence spectrometer equipped with an integrating sphere. The inner surface of the sphere was coated with BENFLEC (Edinburgh Instruments, UK). Liquid samples were placed in a 10 mm path-length UV quartz glass cuvette (Starna, Germany). A blank measurement was performed using the same cuvette filled with solvent only for reference. Spectral correction curves, accounting for the spectral response of the monochromator, detector, sphere coating, and optical components, were provided by Edinburgh Instruments. The accuracy of the integrating sphere setup was validated using reference dyes with known QY values: 2-aminopyridine (Aldrich) was measured as 84%, consistent with the reference

QY of 84%; 4-(dicyanomethylene)-2-methyl-6-(4-dimethylaminostyryl)-4H-pyran in DMSO (Aldrich) the measured fluorescence QY matched the reference value of 57%; and for Rhodamine 101 (Exciton) with a reference QY of 100%, a measured fluorescence QY of 99% was obtained.

Real-time pH tracking in a solution with dynamically changing pH

To track real-time pH changes in a dynamically changing solution, a NaOH crystal was placed inside a syringe fitted with a membrane filter, with the syringe needle immersed in a cuvette with RhB-CDs dilute solution. The measurement commenced when 1 mL of the RhB-CD solution was drawn into the syringe, initiating the gradual dissolution of NaOH and the subsequent slow pH shift in the RhB-CD-containing solution in the cuvette. The value of pH was tracked in real time every 10 min, correlating fluorescence lifetime measurements of CDs with solution pH using a pre-established calibration curve.

Cell culture

BJ human skin fibroblast cells CRL-2522 (ATCC, USA) were cultured in EMEM (Sigma Aldrich, USA) supplemented with L-Glutamine (2 mM), non-essential amino acids (NEAA, 1x), fetal bovine serum (FBS, 10%), PenStrep (5 U/mL penicillin, 50 µg/mL streptomycin) and sodium bicarbonate (2 g/L) at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂-enriched atmosphere.

In vitro cell viability

Cell viability was assessed using a FACSVerse flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, USA). BJ cells were seeded in a 24-well plate at a density of 5×10^4 cells/well and incubated overnight. The following day, cells were treated with 100 or 200 µg/mL of RhB-CDs for 48 hours. Viability was analyzed a live/dead assay with two fluorescent markers. After incubation, the culture supernatant was collected, the cells were gently washed with pre-warmed PBS (0.1 M, pH 7.4), detached using trypsin (0.25% in EDTA, Sigma Aldrich), and resuspended in a complete culture medium supplemented with propidium iodide solution (10 µg/mL, Thermo Fisher) and calcein-AM (50 µM, Thermo Fisher). Cells were incubated for 30 min before analysis. Heat-treated cells (60°C for 10 min) served as positive control (PC), and untreated cells as a negative control (NC). Additional controls were introduced to prevent material interference, as previously described (Malina et al., 2021).

In vitro confocal fluorescence imaging

Cell uptake analysis and confocal imaging were performed after 48 h of incubation using Zeiss LSM980 confocal microscope with Airyscan 2 (Zeiss, Germany). BJ cells were seeded in a µ-Slide 8-well IbiTreat chamber (Ibidi, Germany) at a density 5×10^4 cells/well and allowed to adhere overnight. The next day, cells were treated with 200 µg/mL RhB-CDs for 48 h. After incubation, the supernatant was removed, and cells were gently washed with warm PBS (0.1 M, pH 7.4). Lysosomes were stained after incubation with RhB-CDs using Lysosomal Staining Kit (Abcam, UK) for 60 min according to the manufacturer's protocol. Following the staining, the medium was discarded, cells were rinsed with PBS, fresh medium was added, and lysosomes and RhB-CDs were imaged by confocal fluorescence microscope. The green ($\lambda_{ex} = 488$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 503$ – 553 nm) and red ($\lambda_{ex} = 594$ nm, $\lambda_{em} = 605$ – 700 nm) emission signals were collected selectively using the dedicated detector channel.

Table S1. Comparison of the state-of-the-art fluorescence lifetime-based pH (nano)sensors reported in literature and developed in this work (RhB-CDs).

Sample	Ref.	Emission color, QY	Ease of Synthesis	Toxicity, Biocompatibility	pH Range	Stability
CDs	Huang, 2020	Orange, QY=46%	Hydrothermal method using hazardous and ecotoxic solvent (DMF)	Redispersed in DMSO; satisfactory cytotoxicity only at low concentration (50 µg/mL)	5.0–7.5; high calibration uncertainties	Water-insoluble
MPA@CdSe/ZnS QDs	Orte, 2013	Green, QY n/a	Commercial QDs, ligand exchanged	Contain Cd; cytotoxicity n/a	6.5–7.5; calibration uncertainties	Unstable after 1 month; unstable at low pH
CdSe/ZnS QDs	Herrera-Ochoa, 2022	Red, QY~30%	Commercial QDs, functionalized	Contain Cd; cytotoxic at 200 µg/mL	6.2–7.5; high calibration uncertainties	Low chemical stability aggregation tendency
Lanthanide complexes	Ning, 2019	NIR, QY n/a	Complex lanthanide coordination chemistry	Satisfactory cytotoxicity only at low concentrations	6.0–7.2; high calibration uncertainties	Aggregates at pH < 5
Fluorescent protein RpHLuorin2	Linders, 2022	Green, QY n/a	Synthetic gene expression <i>via</i> molecular cloning	Cytotoxicity n/a	4.9–7.5; high calibration uncertainties	Stability n/a
RhB-CDs (this work)	-	Green, QY=56%	One-step hydrothermal method, single precursor	Low cytotoxicity; water-soluble	1.0–11.0; pseudo-linear response, high calibration accuracy	>20 months storage stability >1 month stability at pH 1 and pH 14

Abbreviations:

PL: photoluminescence; **QY:** quantum yield; **CDs:** carbon dots; **DMF:** dimethylformamide; **DMSO:** dimethyl sulfoxide; **MPA:** mercaptopropionic acid; **QDs:** quantum dots; **n/a:** not available; **NIR:** near-infrared; **RhB:** Rhodamine B.

Fig. S1. Effect of liquid-to-solid (water-to-ice) phase transition of the solvent on steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence of RhB-CDs. (a) Fluorescence intensity in the liquid (red curve) and solid (ice; blue curve) states. Strong Rayleigh scattering of excitation light is marked as a (*). (b) Fluorescence decays recorded in the liquid (red curve) and solid (ice; blue curve) states at the maximum emission wavelength, with experimental data shown as symbols and the stretched exponential fits represented by solid lines.

Fig. S2. pH-dependent transient fluorescence of RhB-CDs. (a-c) Normalized spectrally and time-resolved emission color maps at pH 1, pH 7, and pH 11. (d) Extracted wavelength-dependent fluorescence lifetime at pH 1, pH 7, and pH 11.

Fig. S3. One-month stability of RhB-CDs under strongly acidic and basic conditions. (a) Fluorescence decay of RhB-CDs at strongly acidic conditions (pH 1) for initial sample (black line) and the same sample after 1 month of storage (green line). (b) Fluorescence decay of RhB-CDs at strongly basic conditions (pH 14) for initial sample (black line) and the same sample after 1 month of storage (green line). All fluorescence decays were collected at the emission maximum, with experimental data shown as symbols and the stretched exponential fit represented by a solid line.

Fig. S4. Twenty-month storage stability of RhB-CDs. (a, b) Absolute fluorescence QY measurements for the as-synthesized sample (a) and the same sample after 20 months of storage at room temperature in the dark (b). (c) Fluorescence lifetime decay measurements of the same sample, comparing the as-synthesized sample (blue symbols) with the sample after 20 months of storage at room temperature in the dark (green symbols).

Fig. S5. Batch-to-batch reproducibility of RhB-CDs. (a, b) Absolute fluorescence QY measurements for original batch sample (a) and new batch sample (b), both at pH 11 and produced under identical synthesis conditions. (c) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves of from original batch (blue symbols) and a new batch (red symbols), both dispersed in ultrapure water and produced under identical synthesis conditions.

Fig. S6. Stability of RhB-CDs in a fetal bovine serum (FBS) supplemented phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves recorded over 7 days. (b) Corresponding fluorescence lifetime stability during the 7-day period.

Fig. S7. Stability of RhB-CDs in 1 wt% PEG 2000 solution. (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves recorded over 7 days. (b) Corresponding fluorescence lifetime stability during the 7-day period.

Fig. S8. Stability of RhB-CDs in 1 wt% PEG 35000 solution. (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves recorded over 7 days. (b) Corresponding fluorescence lifetime stability during the 7-day period.

Fig. S9. Stability of RhB-CDs in 5 wt% PEG 2000 solution. (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves recorded over 7 days. (b) Corresponding fluorescence lifetime stability during the 7-day period.

Fig. S10. Stability of RhB-CDs in 5 wt% PEG 35000 solution. (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay curves recorded over 7 days. (b) Corresponding fluorescence lifetime stability during the 7-day period.

Fig. S11. Fluorescence microscopy images of BJ cells confirming the biocompatibility of RhB-CDs. BJ cells stained with Hoechst (a blue-fluorescent dye for DNA staining) alone (a) and co-stained with RhB-CDs and Hoechst (b). Images were captured using the blue and green detector channels, as well as bright field imaging. The final image shown are merged image of these individual channels.

Fig. S12. Confocal fluorescence microscopy of BJ cells for intracellular signal confirmation. 2.5D display from Z-stack of BJ cell co-stained with RhB-CDs and lysosomal staining kit. The image is merged from two images obtained from the green (corresponds to RhB-CDs) and red (corresponds to LysoTracker) detector channels.

Fig. S13. In vitro pH imaging of BJ cells using FLIM with RhB-CDs. (a,b) Fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) image of BJ cells incubated with RhB-CDs: control cells (a), and same cells incubated with RhB-CDs ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 24 h (b). FLIM maps are visualized using an arbitrary color scale representing the average fluorescence lifetime range, with brightness indicating the signal intensity.

Table S2. Exponential fit parameters describing the pH dependence of nonradiative PL decay rates (Figure 4b) obtained using the fitting function $y = y_0 + A \cdot \exp(R_0 \cdot x)$. The adjusted R^2 value for the fit is 0.98785.

Parameter	Value	Standard Error
y_0	-0.82202	0.60813
A	5.37856	0.48343
R_0	-0.14729	0.03674

Table S3. Exponential fit parameters describing the pH dependence of radiative PL decay rates (see Figure 4b) obtained using the fitting function $y = y_0 + A \cdot \exp(R_0 \cdot x)$. The adjusted R^2 value for the fit is 0.96427.

Parameter	Value	Standard Error
y_0	3.11405	1.20935
A	-3.39395	1.07513
R_0	-0.09835	0.06072

Fig. S14. High-resolution FLIM images of lysosomes in BJ cells incubated with RhB-CDs (200 μg/ml) for 48 h: either in the absence (a) or presence (b) of the V-ATPase inhibitor bafilomycin A1 (Baf. A1). 10 randomly selected lysosomes from each condition are highlighted, with numbering corresponding to Table S4.

Table S4. Fluorescence decay fittings results and corresponding pH values for lysosomes labeled in Figure S7 in BJ cells incubated with RhB-CDs ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 48 h, either in the absence (points 1–10) or presence (points 11–20) of the V-ATPase inhibitor bafilomycin A1 (Baf. A1), as determined using calibration Equation 1 from the main text.

Point	$B_1, \%$	τ_1, ns	$B_2, \%$	τ_2, ns	$\tau_{\text{avg}}, \text{ns}$	χ^2	pH
BJ cells incubated with RhB-CDs ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 48 h), no inhibitor							
1	38.6	4.300 ± 0.08	61.4	0.962 ± 0.072	3.46 ± 0.01	1.047	4.35 ± 0.03
2	32.0	4.230 ± 0.06	68.0	0.805 ± 0.032	3.23 ± 0.03	1.102	3.50 ± 0.11
3	35.1	4.330 ± 0.04	64.9	0.894 ± 0.028	3.39 ± 0.02	1.020	4.08 ± 0.08
4	25.6	4.310 ± 0.07	74.4	0.599 ± 0.014	3.24 ± 0.02	1.048	3.53 ± 0.07
5	36.7	4.340 ± 0.07	63.3	0.807 ± 0.017	3.48 ± 0.03	1.097	4.42 ± 0.12
6	34.7	4.350 ± 0.07	65.3	0.850 ± 0.030	3.41 ± 0.03	1.024	4.15 ± 0.12
7	26.1	4.500 ± 0.10	73.9	0.840 ± 0.040	3.19 ± 0.05	1.020	3.36 ± 0.17
8	36.4	4.160 ± 0.09	63.6	0.799 ± 0.053	3.31 ± 0.02	1.036	3.78 ± 0.07
9	31.5	4.400 ± 0.06	68.5	0.762 ± 0.038	3.42 ± 0.01	1.029	4.19 ± 0.04
10	31.3	4.500 ± 0.11	68.7	0.980 ± 0.080	3.37 ± 0.02	1.028	4.00 ± 0.08
BJ cells incubated with RhB-CDs ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 48 h), inhibitor Baf. A1							
11	62.2	4.520 ± 0.05	37.8	1.550 ± 0.090	4.01 ± 0.02	1.058	7.06 ± 0.12
12	62.1	4.420 ± 0.06	37.9	1.550 ± 0.090	3.91 ± 0.02	0.982	6.48 ± 0.11
13	57.4	4.560 ± 0.05	42.6	1.330 ± 0.060	4.00 ± 0.01	1.133	7.00 ± 0.06
14	55.3	4.540 ± 0.06	44.7	1.200 ± 0.090	3.95 ± 0.03	1.049	6.70 ± 0.17
15	56.7	4.640 ± 0.05	43.3	1.430 ± 0.080	4.03 ± 0.01	1.022	7.18 ± 0.06
16	60.6	4.480 ± 0.04	39.4	1.470 ± 0.040	3.95 ± 0.04	1.007	6.70 ± 0.23
17	59.0	4.640 ± 0.04	41.0	1.400 ± 0.070	4.07 ± 0.01	0.992	7.43 ± 0.06
18	59.5	4.600 ± 0.04	40.5	1.410 ± 0.060	4.00 ± 0.01	1.095	7.00 ± 0.06
19	58.6	4.650 ± 0.06	41.6	1.500 ± 0.100	4.07 ± 0.02	1.044	7.43 ± 0.13
20	60.1	4.530 ± 0.04	39.9	1.360 ± 0.040	4.00 ± 0.01	1.050	7.00 ± 0.06

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